

SUPER-CONTRACT: SOCIAL JUSTICE IN ACCESS TO HIGHER EDUCATION OR A LEGITIZED FORM OF CORRUPTION?

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Abstract: This article analyzes the legal foundations of the differentiated tuition fee (super-contract) system in the higher education system of Uzbekistan and its impact on the principles of social justice in society. The role of the system in reducing corruption and, at the same time, the potential risks of creating economic inequality are comparatively studied.

Keywords: Super-contract, higher education, corruption, social justice, legal equality, economics of education.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируются правовые основы системы дифференцированной платно-контрактной формы обучения (супер-контракт) в системе высшего образования Узбекистана и её влияние на принципы социальной справедливости в обществе. В сравнительном аспекте изучается роль системы в снижении коррупции и, в то же время, вероятность возникновения экономического неравенства.

Ключевые слова: Супер-контракт, высшее образование, коррупция, социальная справедливость, правовое равенство, экономика образования.

In recent years, the increase in the coverage of higher education and the introduction of a differentiated contract system have given rise to different views among the public. On the one hand, the system increases revenue to the state budget, on the other hand, it poses a risk of violating the principle of meritocracy. This contradictory situation requires a thorough analysis of the legal nature of the system. Therefore, this article examines the effectiveness of the super-contract system in the fight against corruption and legal solutions based on international experience.

If we pay attention to foreign experience, in particular, in the country of Singapore, this system does not exist. In other words, in Singapore, a system that is different from this system and is much more transparent is used. More precisely, in this country, grants are announced in order to increase the coverage of the higher education system, and if a student cannot get a place in these places, he can become a student through a contract. That is, if the student is talented, the state pays for his education. If the student's knowledge is not enough to get a place in these places, he will cover the tuition fees himself. Students who fail the exam or score low will be able to apply to private educational institutions. If a student fails to score the minimum score, he will not be accepted for higher education at any cost. This, in turn, ensures transparency in education by supporting talented students. That is, to study in Singapore, knowledge and high scores are needed first of all. The money will only serve to cover the cost of education, not to compensate for low scores [1].

In the Turkish experience, additional opportunities are created for students through the "second education" (İkinci Öğretim) mechanism, which serves to expand the financial capabilities of universities. However, there is no differentiated payment-contract system in the Singaporean higher education system either. The basis of financing universities or education is

carried out by this state through evening education. The reason is that full-time education is almost free or very cheap, and evening education is more expensive (on a contract basis).

If we turn to the situation in the higher education system of Uzbekistan, if we accept the differentiated payment-contract in a certain sense as a privilege or opportunity, how can we explain the negative and positive impact of this reform on legal areas that require high knowledge and deep qualifications? However, it is important to remember one important aspect: the government has also established certain academic restrictions for this system. More specifically, the fact that even in order to be accepted as a student on a differentiated payment contract, an applicant must have achieved a minimum passing score (56.7 points) means that we do not view this system solely as a source of pure funding [2].

In general, the above-mentioned foreign countries have a strict approach to the principles of meritocracy, which legally and economically proves the need to transform education into a sustainable development trend, not a source of financing, as the higher education system provides intellectual personnel for the future of the state.

If we analyze the processes in the higher education system of Uzbekistan before this systemic reform, it becomes clear that one of the main problems was the lack of transparency in the admissions process. In particular, there is a fundamental legal difference between the cases of student recruitment through "hidden corruption" (subjective factors, artificial barriers and acquaintances) observed in previous periods and the current open and official payment system. These processes, which previously became a source of illegal income for some individuals, have today been legalized through a differentiated payment-contract system. This ensures that funds received from individuals and legal entities are directed not to personal pockets, but to the direct financing of educational institutions under state control, effectively limiting corruption risks in the system.

As a clear example of this, more than 30 leading higher educational institutions in Uzbekistan have been transferred to a self-financing system since 2020 [3]. From 15 to 20 percent of the total income of these higher education institutions is accounted for by stratified (super) contracts. Previously, these funds remained in the shadows and served to develop the underground economy, but now they are being spent on strengthening the material and technical base of universities. In addition, since super-contract payments are made through official bank transfers, the State Treasury controls the targeted use of every soum. Consequently, since 2017, the number of crimes related to entrance exams has decreased by 80-90 percent, according to official reports of law enforcement agencies [4]. If in 2016 the level of coverage of higher education in Uzbekistan was only 9 percent, by 2024 this figure exceeded 40 percent [5]. These figures prove not only the legal but also the strong socio-economic effectiveness of abandoning the underground economy.

At this point, let us stop at the question: "Is the differentiated payment contract a formalized form of corruption?" from a legal perspective. One of the aspects being analyzed is the public nature and legality of the opportunity. While the previously existing secret system provided opportunities only to those with large amounts of money or subjective acquaintance with criminal means, the differentiated contract system provides equal opportunities to all citizens within the framework of the law. The fact that currently, state and university grants and incentive scholarships are being allocated to talented and low-income students at the expense of funds received from the super-contract is an example of the social orientation of this system [6]. In addition, the increase in the salaries and bonuses of the teaching staff at the expense of this source of financing indirectly serves to improve the quality of education.

However, taking into account all the positive aspects, the possibility that the differentiated contract system may cause disproportionate social stratification in society should not be excluded from legal analysis. The fact that a child from a family with a lower level of education but higher financial means is actually "outperformed" by a talented and educated, but

economically disadvantaged applicant does not fully comply with the principles of social justice and equality. After all, Article 41 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan stipulates that everyone has the right to education and that the state guarantees free general education, and ensuring the criteria of social equality and justice in the higher education system is one of the constitutional obligations of a social state [7].

At the same time, the systemic flaws in the process of training qualified personnel in the future are also an undeniable fact. For example, how much legal basis does the implementation of this system have in the areas of jurisprudence, which is considered a profession of justice in society? Until recent years, this differentiated system also existed in the field of medicine, but since it is associated with human life, it did not justify itself and restrictions were imposed. If we do not trust the lives and health of people to unqualified personnel, why have we still fully preserved this mechanism in the system of training professional lawyers who are defenders of justice and ensure the rule of law?

It is true that the differentiated payment-contract curbed and limited corruption in a certain transitional period, but this system cannot serve the education strategy forever in the long term. In order to build a developed legal state, it is better to completely eliminate corruption and achieve it step by step, rather than to contain it with economic means for a certain period of time. High funding of higher education institutions cannot be an absolute guarantee of independently producing high-quality professional personnel.

Today, the differentiated payment-contract system is fully consistent with the current legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan and is legal. The initial regulatory and legal basis of this system is the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-2955 dated May 5, 2017 [8]. Also, the legal nature of this system is further strengthened by Article 48 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" (Provision of paid services by educational organizations) and the relevant regulatory regulations of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan [9]. In particular, the transition of higher educational institutions to a certain degree of financial and academic independence has legally regulated the mechanism for setting differentiated payment rates and liberalizing their amounts [10].

Based on the above, the following proposals and conclusions can be put forward:

1. Introduce a system of further differentiation of the amount of the differentiated payment-contract (super-contract) in proportion to the score scored by the applicant in the exam (i.e., the closer and higher the applicant's score is to the passing line, the more the amount of the super-contract paid should be reduced);
2. Establish a legal obligation to allocate at least 30 percent of the total funds received by higher education institutions from the super-contract system to financially encourage and cover the educational contracts of students in need of social protection, true orphans, disabled people, and talented students.

In conclusion, it should be noted that, although the differentiated payment-contract system serves to expand opportunities for higher education, it must not negatively affect the quality of professional personnel in areas such as jurisprudence, which are strategic and important for public administration. In this direction, the gradual improvement of the admission system or its coordination with strict academic requirements (for example, GPA indicators, strengthening the system of retention from course to course) is the main guarantee of transferring the state legal system to qualified specialists in the future and establishing the principle of constitutional social justice in society. After all, the priority of quality, not quantity, is of great importance in ensuring jurisprudence and the rule of law.

Also, expanding legal mechanisms to assist admitted students in making contract payments will allow for further improvement of the education system. This requires further simplification of the system for allocating educational loans, established by the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-323 dated July 18, 2022 [11]. Simplification of educational

loan mechanisms will not only ease the financial burden of families, but also serve to expand the intellectual layer of society. Liberalizing loan terms by commercial banks and further strengthening the state guarantee system will transform the super-contract system from a purely commercial project into a socially protected education model.

In conclusion, any financial reforms in the education system should serve not to reduce the level of knowledge of students, but to fairly expand the opportunities for obtaining quality higher education for all segments of society - this is the main guarantee of the rule of law and sustainable democratic development in the country.

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